

Semantic x-Lab:

Bridging Laboratory Metadata and Semantic Knowledge Discovery

Oliver Knodel, David Pape, Martin Voigt, Marc Hanisch, Felix Mühlbauer, Manja Luzi-Helbing

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www.helmholtz-metadaten.de

Welcome & Agenda

Agenda

- Part I: Introduction and use cases
 - Introduction round
 - The Semantic x-Lab project
 - Use cases at HZDR and GFZ
 - Discussion
- Break ☕ 🍪
- Part II: Hack session (in parallel groups 👥)
 - Group 1: Knowledge Graph User Interaction
 - Group 2: Knowledge Graph Infrastructure
- Wrap-up
- Closing

Introduction round

- Have you ever worked with knowledge graphs?

Introduction

- Collect your questions and assign them to the groups

Visualization of interaction with knowledge graph

Infrastructure

Miscellaneous

interesting related stuff

Infrastructure

interesting related stuff

Integration with ELNs ?
ELNs often don't have a semantic layer !

Miscellaneous

when starting using an ontology? from beginning vs. map later

ELNs typically do not support ontologies

How can we avoid to develop multiple obs in parallel ?

repetitive have different schemes and min. required fields

internal vs. published subdata

Poly Lab Ontology coming (hopefully) next month

I. How it started

The HELIPORT project in 2020

HELIPORT — The Helmholtz Scientific Workflow Platform (Cohort 2020)

“ The HELIPORT project aims at developing a platform which accommodates the **life cycle** of a scientific project and links all corresponding programs, **systems** and **workflows** to create a more **FAIR and comprehensible** project description.

Fields:

Project Members:

HELIPORT HELmholtz Scientific
Project WOrkflow PlatForm

Funded by:


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{
  "namespaces": {
    "datacite": "http://purl.org/spar/datacite/",
    "rdf": "http://www.w3.org/2000/05/rdf-schema#",
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    "time": "http://www.w3.org/2006/time#",
    "dc": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/"
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  "heliport:project_id": 28,
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  "heliport:uid": "89779261-200c-48c4-b0fc-f29836966a1c",
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  "heliport:project_name": "P908 Research Project",
  "time:hasBeginning": "2021-04-01 09:14:34.296524+00:00",
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  "heliport:owner": {
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    "rdfs:label": "Knodel, Dr. Oliver (FWCC) - 132739"
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  },
  "heliport:has_DataSource": {
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    "datacite:hasDescription": "dddd"
  }
}
```

HELIPORT and the Full Data Management Lifecycle at HZDR

II. How it continued

The ALAMEDA project in 2021

ALAMEDA — A Scalable Multi-Domain Metadata Management Platform (Cohort 2021)

“ The ALAMEDA data management environment covers five main categories of metadata: **observations** and measurements, **samples** and data history, **sensors** and devices, **methods** and processing, and **environmental properties**.

Project Members:

Observer:

Funded by:

ALAMEDA — Data Management with “ALAMEDA Helicopter”

IV. Where we are now and what comes next

The joint project Semantic x-Lab (2024)

Semantic x-Lab — Something with Metadata and Knowledge Graphs (Cohort 2024)

“ Semantic x-Lab aims to **interlink** and **contextualise** the metadata from four institutes and two research fields through a distributed **knowledge graph** developed in collaboration with users, enabling **cross-domain exploration** and the generation of **new insights**.

Fields:

Project Members:

Observer:

Funded by:

Semantic x-Lab — The Benefits and Opportunities for Laboratories and Experiments

When as much information as possible of an experiment are incorporated into a **knowledge graph**:

- Previously **unknown connections** between **different disciplines** are suddenly visible
- **Project planning** becomes easier because there is a clear view of what others with **similar processes** have done
- Same **sample** in other research areas and further knowledge
- Additional **references** for publications from previously unknown **connected scientific fields** and topics
- Knowledge base for further **LLMs**

Source: search.unhide.helmholtz-metadaten.de

Semantic x-Lab — The Vision

Planned ecosystem:

- Distributed knowledge graph connects **internal** and **external metadata sources**
- Approval and curation of metadata for (external) use by the owner via a **knowledge editor**
- Internal **search and discovery**
- Cross-institutional connections and relations

Outcome

- Making new, previously **unknown relationships** visible
- Provision of **curated KG** for the next levels (e.g. Helmholtz KG)

Semantic x-Lab — The Plan

WP1

Definition of concepts for a knowledge graph of **interlinked metadata** with established, application-specific ontologies and implementation of a **local graph database** infrastructure

WP2

Integration of existing and new laboratory **BPMN workflows**, tools, **services** and **data repositories** into the ontologies

WP3

Graph database-driven search and discovery service provided by knowledge editors for typical scientific use-cases at RIs

WP4

Public **metadata endpoints (API)** that follow FAIR principles for interlinked metadata Integration of external data sources

WP5

Outlook towards an advanced search in community standards and future extensions

WP6

Considerations and guidelines for long-term adoption of Semantic x-Lab infrastructure at RIs and onboarding of new metadata providers

WP7

Project & Community Management

HELMHOLTZKG

**Semantic
x-Lab**

First step: Semantic x-Lab — Kick-Off Workshop

- Introduction of the project and the team using distributed knowledge graphs (in Miro)
- Live SPARQL queries to show interactions and possibilities

- Presentation of Use Cases from Pilot Laboratories:
 - **GFZ**: Determination of stable metal(loid) isotopes in soil samples
 - **HZDR**: High-Power Laser-Plasma-Experiments (HPL)
- Practical session “Build your own (tiny) knowledge graph for your experiment”:

- Presentations to provide insights into knowledge graphs from **Helmholtz KG** and **KG4NFDI**

Conclusion: We need a follow-up workshop...

Definition of Use Cases and Uniform Description — Soil Sample at GFZ

- The GFZ Use Case: **Magnesium (Mg) isotope analysis of soil samples:**

Legende:

Definition of Use Cases and Uniform Description — LPA at HZDR, GSI, HIJ

- The HZDR Use Case: **Laser Plasma Acceleration (LPA)**
- Challenge: Structured documentation of the current status of **experiment** and **simulation** (digital twin)

Insight: We should start with something simpler or reduce the complexity...

Use Cases

Magnesium Isotopes

Laser Particle Acceleration (LPA)

Nano Contact Platform (NCP)

Real-live Use Cases for the Semantic x-Lab Project

- Magnesium Isotopes
- Laser Plasma Acceleration (LPA)
- Cleanroom Process (NCP)

Magnesium (Mg) isotope analysis of soil samples

Planning phase Sampling phase Sample preparation Analysis Evaluation Publication

Laser Plasma Acceleration (LPA)

Nano Contact Platform (NCP) production

Discussion

Your Input

Discussion

- Do you have similar use cases within your projects?
- Did we cover everything?
- Which aspects are important to you?

Interactive Session

Work in Parallel Groups

Interactive Session

Group 1: Knowledge Graph User Interaction

- How to query the KG?
- How to visualise results?
- How to add to the KG?

Group 2: Knowledge Graph Infrastructure

- Data ingestion
- Integration with 3rd-party systems
- Interfaces and mappings

Wrap-up and Closing

Wrap-Up – Outcomes from the Groups

Group 1: Knowledge Graph User Interaction I

How to query the knowledge graph

- Prefer natural language over SPARQL due to lab staff unfamiliarity
- Pre-defined queries with dropdown parameters and static English descriptions
- LLM-based options range from query generation to full agentic workflows
- PaN-Finder as an example: free-text input returning datasets with relevance explanations
- MCP enables LLM access to lab systems and knowledge graph querying
- Agentic workflows: unclear task division for concept exploration and query generation

How to visualise responses

- Visualisation depends on type of data
- Additional feature (downloads of tabular data, hyperlinks to external systems) would be helpful

How to add data to the KG

- Distinguish new data addition vs error correction
- New data: automated processes preferred
- Errors: resolve at source
- Ownership/stewardship of shared knowledge graph statements unclear

Group 1: Knowledge Graph User Interaction II

Examples from your labs

How to Visualize Responses?

How to Query the Knowledge Graph?

How to Add Data to the Knowledge Graph?

Group 2: Knowledge Graph Infrastructure I

- Persistent Identifiers are of particular importance to knowledge graph interfaces and in connecting information:
 - PID systems for specific types of objects exist (see e.g. record type “identifier schema” in <https://fairsharing.org>). Some types of objects do not yet have an established corresponding PID system (Platforms, Observatories, Laboratory, ...).
 - Persons have different local identifiers that may be mappable to ORCID.
- Research systems that could be relevant for being harvested into a knowledge graph include data management plans, ELNs, lab information management systems, research data management services / data catalogues, discovery services, archiving solutions, reporting infrastructures:
 - They often don't already have a semantic layer.
- Have common semantic model where concepts at different services (such as ELN) can map to:
 - Existing models include [ISA](#), existing minimum information profiles include [MixS](#) for Genome sequences.

Group 2: Knowledge Graph Infrastructure II

Community Activation — Part II: Possible ways to proceed

Closing

Closing

- Thank you for your active participation!
- We will incorporate the outcomes of these discussions into our next steps within the project